

AI-ENHANCED STORYTELLING IN ENGLISH: PROJECT-BASED LEARNING FOR 21ST CENTURY SKILLS

VALERIYA I. IVANOVA

Abstract: This article explores the use of project-based learning (PBL) and technology in English language classrooms to enhance 21st-century skills such as creativity, critical thinking, communication and technology literacy. It presents the outcomes of a project-based learning activity where students create stories and sequels illustrating them using AI-generated images. The project highlighted the potential of PBL to foster collaboration, innovation, and engagement while addressing challenges like ethical use and digital proficiency. It concludes with recommendations for integrating AI into education to prepare students for an increasingly AI-driven world.

Keywords: *AI in Education, 21st-Century Skills, Creativity, Project-Based Learning, Technology Literacy, English language*

In today's dynamic educational landscape, equipping students with language skills alone is no longer sufficient. Creativity, teamwork, and technology literacy are essential for building 21st-century competencies. Research indicates that 21st-century skills encompass creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and digital literacy, which are necessary for success in modern education and careers [2]. Studies have shown that integrating these skills into classroom activities prepares students for the demands of the 21st-century workplace and fosters their ability to solve complex problems [3]. Additionally, research has demonstrated that project-based learning and technology-enhanced activities can effectively develop these crucial competencies in students [4]. This article presents some insights from project-based learning carried out with the support of technology. Recently, I had the opportunity to run an ESL storytelling project with 12 students, designed to strengthen these essential skills. This project combined storytelling with AI-generated images, giving students a creative platform to review and practice past simple and past perfect

tense structures and writing while engaging with digital tools. The goal was to create student-centered activities that increase learners' enthusiasm and give them greater autonomy in their educational journey. Student-centered activities and project-based learning have shown significant promise in enhancing language courses. Research indicates that learner-centered classrooms actively engage students in various activities and improve learning outcomes [5]. Specifically, project-based activities positively impact students' engagement and dedication in language classes [5]. For instance, a study at the South East European University (SEEU) involving sixty students in an ESP course found that group projects fostered more positive attitudes towards the class, and increased motivation, and enthusiasm among students [5]. These activities also helped improve critical and creative thinking skills, teamwork, and the ability to provide constructive criticism[5].

Methodology: the article presents a qualitative study (discussion, observation) of students from *Konstantin Preslavsky* University of Shumen, Bulgaria. All students are female, second year in major Primary School Education with English. The lesson was designed to review past simple and past perfect tense in a General English class (B1 level)., to develop writing as well as group work, creativity, and digital skills. Students were divided into three groups, each assigned 10 random images. Their task was to write a coherent story within 40 minutes, using the images as inspiration, and write a story using them as illustration guidelines. Subsequently, each student independently created a sequel to their group's story, incorporating their unique perspective. To visualize their sequels, students utilized an AI image generator, blending modern technology with their language learning experience.

Image 1. Story created by group 1 based on 10 random images

Discussion and results

After finishing their group stories, students moved on to the next step: creating individual sequels and presenting them before class as presentations. Each student continued the narrative from their group's story, building on the established events and themes while adding their unique perspective and style. This individual writing task allowed students to expand on the collaborative foundation while expressing their creativity. Several students demonstrated exceptional creativity by crafting unique and engaging sequels to the original story. Their work showcased individuality and personal flair, resulting in diverse and compelling narratives.

Image 2
Presentation Student 1

Image 3
Presentation Student 2

To maintain narrative coherence, students were instructed to consistently use past simple and past perfect tenses, ensuring clarity and smooth storytelling. These individual sequels, ranging from 300 to 1000 words, pushed students to explore deeper aspects of storytelling, including character development, plot progression, and personal writing style.

The process also promoted self-expression and individual creativity. While the group stories provided a shared framework, the sequels allowed each student to explore different plot twists, reveal hidden character motives, or introduce new settings. Below are presented two AI-generated images from different students illustrating the variety of creative perspectives. Each student's image uniquely reflected their personal interpretation of the same story.

After the end of the project, students presented their sequels and discussed some of the challenges they had met.

As part of their project to write their sequels, each student created several images to complement their story using an AI image generator. Students received a brief tutorial on the platform, with instructions on how to use descriptive language to prompt the AI. In the tutorial I used for the DeepAI, however, I allowed them to use whatever AI they felt comfortable with. After the presentations, we discussed some aspects related to the project.

Image 4
AI-generated image - student
1

Image 5
AI-generated image - Student
2

Before introducing the AI and giving them the necessary introduction I asked them how many have used AI before that. Only 1 of the 12 students reported that she hadn't. After they presented the stories I inquired which AI they used. They used different AI tools such as ChatGPT, DeepAI, and Pixlr. The majority used ChatGPT which is normal as it is the most popular among them.

The exercise encouraged students to think visually and to consider how images could enhance narrative storytelling. It also gave them hands-on experience with digital tools, aligning with the project's goal of integrating technology into the learning process. One of the aspects we as university professors and teacher trainers need to develop in our students is the opportunity that AI presents before us, as well as curiosity and what it can do to enhance our teaching practices.

Technology literacy

The project involves technology which is why we can't omit the issue related to students' creativity, digital literacy and proficiency. After the project's end, students took part in a discussion about its results. Below are some of the answers to the following question "What was it like to use AI to create images for your story? How did these visuals influence the way you thought about your story, if at all?"

"The experience wasn't perfect but it did an overall good job."

"It was tiring at first because it kept on making the images a little different. But It was interesting."

"Not in any way."

"Sort of challenging to get details relating to stories"

Students generally responded positively to using AI, but they encountered difficulties generating images with consistent characters. When asked why they didn't use alternative software like Photoshop to change what they didn't like, students admitted they hadn't considered it. This observation raises important questions about their current digital literacy and proficiency and do they need additional ICT training. Apart from their digital skills, the project-based learning allowed them to improve their presentation skills as well.

They were also asked, "What did you use AI for to create your project? (text, image, or other functionalities)". The majority used AI for image generation, only 1 student admitted that she has used it to generate text, and several for text correction as I had instructed them to upload their group stories and instruct the AI to check them for grammar mistakes.

Another aspect which the students who wrote their sequels by themselves raised was "Isn't it cheating when you use AI to generate the story?". We should mention that although it is visible that the students have used AI, none of them referenced it during the presentations. This raised the need for students to be trained about AI and its ethical use. According to Ivanov, I., teacher trainers have the task of not only improving students' digital skills but also preparing them for the challenges related to the application of AI in education. [1]

Collaboration and communication

Students were asked the question: How did working in a group impact the storytelling process? Describe how your group collaborated and handled different ideas or opinions. Their answer varies from person to person but some of them have responded:

"It was honestly difficult working on this task as a group because some people didn't agree with small details that weren't

crucial to the development of the story like names etc. and it slowed down the process."

"It handled ideas or opinions really open-minded."

"The group was very tolerant, and we all respected each other's opinions."

"The idea with the most votes had to be incorporated."

Although group work has its benefits and drawbacks, as teachers in training and employees, they will have to learn how to navigate and find their way with other people to achieve a common goal such as successful project completion.

Creativity and innovation

Providing opportunities for a variety of tasks that involve different skills is very beneficial for future teachers. Project-based learning provides opportunities for the development of different 21st-century skills. Students identify several skills that they have developed during the project among them social skills, storytelling, and creativity. Students were asked: "Which skills do you feel you developed during this project, and how do you think they might be helpful in other areas of your life or studies? ". Some of their answers are:

"We developed our storytelling skills and creativity and they will be helpful."

"Coming up with ideas. It can be helpful during other studies and in life."

"Compliance and social skills. You have to work with people almost everywhere"

Although the number of students is small, overall, the project was successful and my intention to use technology as a tool to develop their 21st-century skills has achieved its goal and students find it useful. However, some of them complained about the time constraints they had to develop and write their initial story.

Conclusion

The integration of AI in education is not just about leveraging technology but about preparing students for the complexities of a rapidly evolving world. Through innovative projects like AI-powered storytelling, we as teacher trainers can

nurture future educators' essential 21st-century skills such as creativity, critical thinking, and digital literacy, which are increasingly vital in academic and professional contexts. This project-based task demonstrated how AI tools can amplify students' creativity and self-expression while fostering collaboration and adaptability. By blending traditional storytelling techniques with cutting-edge technology, students not only improve their language abilities but also gain invaluable insights into the ethical and practical applications of AI, its usability in their future work, communication and presentation skills. As teacher trainers, we must continue exploring the potential of AI to transform learning environments. By doing so, we can empower students to navigate the opportunities and challenges of the digital age with confidence and creativity. The possibilities are endless, and the time to embrace them is now.

References:

1. **Иванов И.**, Повишаване дигиталните компетенции на педагогическите специалисти, Научни трудове том XV – Колеж – Добрич (2023), с. 171-178 <https://www.cceol.com/search/journal-detail?id=4117>
2. **Ariatna, Nuran, A. A., & Soongpankhao, W.** Developing English Teaching Materials Using Task Generator to Enhance The Seventh Graders' English Language And 21st Century Skills. // *JEELS (Journal of English Education and Linguistics Studies*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2023, pp. 407–438. <https://doi.org/10.30762/jeels.v10i2.1751>.
3. **Rahardi, Pangih, et al.** Project-Based Learning in Developing English Language Skills and 21st Century Skills: Students' Voices in Academic Writing Course.// *Metathesis Journal of English Language Literature and Teaching*, 2023.
4. **Shadiev, R., and Xun Wang.** A Review of Research on Technology-Supported Language Learning and 21st Century Skills." // *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 13, 2022.
5. **Zeqiri, Luiza.** Investigating the Influence of Students' Project-Based Engagement on Their Achievements and Their Attitudes Towards the ESP Course // *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, vol. 1, 2015.

[URL:https://chatgpt.com/](https://chatgpt.com/)

[URL:https://deepai.org/machine-learning-model/text2img](https://deepai.org/machine-learning-model/text2img)

[URL:https://pixlr.com/](https://pixlr.com/)